

Omic Biodiversity Observation Network - Omic BON

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Name of BON

Omic BON

Description of the BON

“Omics” refers to the holistic study of elements that compose a greater whole. This term has been most extensively used by the biomolecular community when describing the study of genes, transcripts, proteins, metabolites, and other biomolecules in 1) organisms (genomics, transcriptomics, proteomics, metabolomics, etc.) or 2) environmental materials sampled from ecosystems (**meta**genomics, metatranscriptomics, metaproteomics, environmental DNA [eDNA] analyses, etc). The Omic BON will serve the global omics community through an unprecedented level of open and inclusive coordination: a key element for omics to effectively and sustainably contribute to the global baselines and trusted indicators needed to address pressing threats to the biosphere. We envisage that the Omic BON community will establish decadal strategies and interoperability models, forging sustained links to an ever-growing collection of stakeholders and global programmes, such as the [UN Decade of Ocean Science for Sustainable Development](#) (hereinafter Ocean Decade) and the [UN Decade on Ecosystem Restoration](#). This fundamental step in mainstreaming omic approaches will help build the collective intelligence needed to address grand scientific and societal challenges of our time, from combating pandemics, to restoring biodiversity in the face of climate change.

This Omic BON proposal has previously been introduced at the GEO BON Open Science Conference & All Hands Meeting 2020 to seek input from the broader community prior to its finalisation [https://conf2020.geobon.org/pdf/book-of-abstracts_geobon.pdf p.105].

Key objectives

Global coordination of key actors

- Offer open and inclusive coordination - network of networks
- Align existing and emerging omic observation networks in order to realise greater global impact and prepare for an increasingly automated future
- Work with/draw on expertise of GEO BON's Genetic Composition WG and coordinate efforts involving omics-techniques across all other BONs

Harmonisation of standards and protocols

- Harmonise omic observing globally
- Align omic methods, analysis, and data streams

- Implement and elevate community standards such as the Genomic Standards Consortium's (GSC) Minimum Information about any Sequence (MIxS) and Minimum Information about any Observatory (MIxO) checklists, and TDWGs DarwinCore standard
- Link omic (meta)data to data from other domains
- Elevate omics to effectively and sustainably contribute to the global baselines and trusted indicators needed to address pressing threats to the biosphere

Integration with societal benefit areas

- Integrate omic approaches to provide insights into GEO BON Essential Biodiversity Variables (EBVs)
- Link between omically-enabled GEO BON EBVs and the Essential Ocean Variables (EOVs) by the Global Ocean Observing System (GOOS)
- Bridge science, societal needs, and policy

The Omic BON brings together **strategic partners and collaborators** in a forum which focuses on observatory-grade applications of omic technologies. Partners are drawn from major:

1. **Observatories** - science-led, often national or regional, efforts that are implementing multi-year standards-based omic observation.
2. **Data and Sample Infrastructures** - with the Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF) and Ocean Biodiversity Information System (OBIS) as global biodiversity data networks, and the Global Genome Biodiversity Network (GGBN) uniting many of the major museum collections and biobanks.
3. **Standards and Best-Practice organizations** such as the Genomic Standards Consortium (GSC), Biodiversity Information Standards (TDWG), and IOC's Ocean Best Practices System (OBPS).
4. **Global Earth and Ocean Observing systems** that connect science to policy and society, such as GEO and Global Ocean Observing System (GOOS), for example, via Essential Biodiversity Variables (EBVs) and Essential Ocean Variables (EOVs).

Each partner is independent and makes major contributions in their own right. Omic BON provides an opportunity for them to work together in an open and collaborative forum to:

- Coordinate science-led/research-focused observatories and co-create registries, baselines, exchange standards, and SOPs to accelerate the scientific advances needed to underpin operational omics - including those targeting any biomolecule - in the wider Earth observation system
- Enable international operations-grade omic monitoring inside and outside of the research sector that is connected to other data types (e.g., through GEO BON and

GEO) to address transdisciplinary scientific questions meaningfully, and to reach beyond science to help solve societal challenges globally

Figure 1: High-level positioning of Omic BON across GEO BON, UNESCO, and regional projects and programmes. This draft was generated during the 21st meeting of the Genomic Standards Consortium (GSC 21: May 20-23, 2019) at a satellite meeting on the future directions of the Genomic Observatories Network and Global Omics Observatories Network (GLOMICON) and will be the basis for extension and refinement during the early phases of Omic BON.

Thematic, regional or national BON

The Omic BON is proposed to be a thematic BON. It focuses on a technology and methodology (omics) that enables biodiversity observation at the molecular scale across all environments and geographies. Omic BON will thus complement and contribute to thematic BONs focused on environments ([Marine BON](#), [Freshwater BON](#), [Soil BON](#)), as well as [National and Regional BONs](#). Omic BON will draw on the expertise of the GEO BON [Genetic Composition Working Group](#). Moreover, relevant tools, processes, and standards derived from Omic BON may contribute to BON in a Box.

Acknowledging the cross-cutting nature of this BON, we are eager to proactively engage with the other BON partners in order to efficiently link and realise the full potential of this BON. We'd like to present OMIC BON to other BON leaders at a suitable opportunity (e.g.,

GEO BON Implementation Committee meeting) and would then organize follow-up meetings with individual co-leads according to interest and feedback.

Biodiversity Monitoring Initiatives and Partners Involved

Omic BON is stimulated by the union of:

- Global Omics Observatory Network ([GLOMICON](#))
 - GLOMICON was initialised at an international meeting as part of the H2020 AtlantOS project, which brought together researchers and practitioners who use multi-omic technologies to investigate the biology and ecology of the biosphere (Buttigieg et al., 2019). Collectively, the aim was to support the harmonised development of omics observatories over the world, by promoting best practices, interoperability, coordination, and collective interfaces to other networks. Previous successes include multi-national physical sample exchanges, calibration activities, inter-observatory data exchange, and the development of new publishing models for FAIR omic biodiversity data.
- Genomic Observatories Network ([GOs Network](#))
 - Adopted as a [project](#) of the Genomic Standards Consortium (GSC) in 2012 (Davies, Field, et al., 2012; Davies, Meyer, et al., 2012), the Genomic Observatories Network was formally established in 2014 as a collaboration between GEOBON and the GSC (Bruford et al., 2017; Davies et al., 2014). The network has matured through interaction with projects and programmes such as Autonomous Reef Monitoring Structures (ARMS) (Obst et al., 2020), and Ocean Sampling Day (OSD) (Kopf et al., 2015).

Much of the initial coordination for Omic BON has been in the marine domain (see Figure 2), in part due to the mobilization spurred by the Ocean Decade, but a similar effort is envisaged in the terrestrial domain.

Figure 2. Omic BON is the synthesis of multiple working groups, voluntary networks, and project-based initiatives, providing these with a stable forum for operationalization of multi-omic biodiversity observation. The above provides an example from the marine domain, with a few, stakeholders in this initiative, who have actively engaged with the Omic BON concept.

Membership and Governance

GLOMICON and Genomic Observatories Network provide leadership for Omic BON during its founding phase. We list key partners that we expect to play a leadership role going forward, as well as other organizations that are invited to be involved.

We name organizations here based on their indicated willingness to engage in Omic BON. Once initiated, we will begin to formalize these links, through MoUs and/or other mechanisms as appropriate.

Individual scientists will also be invited to participate. Governance mechanisms remain to be formalized, but suggested structures are outlined below.

Partners and Collaborators

Omic BON will provide an interface for coordination among strategic **Partners and Collaborators** who will form the Omic BON “Leadership Council”. The partners are large, national or international, well-established, regionally, environmentally, and sectorally representative organizations in four critical domains:

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1. **Observatories** - organizations that are operators of long-term sampling programs including (but not limited to) molecular level time-series and that contribute to developing standards and best-practice for the broader community. Initial partners might include:
 - **European Marine Biological Resource Centre (EMBRC)** - for example through its [joint research activity](#) to foster the application of genomics technologies at European Long-Term Ecological Research (LTER) sites.
 - **National Ecological Observatory Network (NEON)** - a continental-scale observation facility operated by Battelle and designed to collect long-term open access ecological data to better understand how U.S. ecosystems are changing.
 - **Australian Microbiome Initiative (AM)** - a continental-scale, collaborative project aspiring to characterise the diversity and ecosystem service provision of the microorganisms inhabiting natural Australian ecosystems.
 - **Smithsonian Marine Global Earth Observatory (MarineGEO)** - a collaborative network of worldwide coastal research partners to catalog the world's coastal marine life, understand how and why it's changing, and the consequences of change for people.
 - **Agriculture and Agri-Food Canada (AAFC)** - supports the Canadian agriculture and agri-food sector through initiatives that promote innovation and competitiveness, and contributed to the founding of GLOMICON.
 2. **Data and Sample Infrastructures** - data repositories¹, aggregators, and portals that include omic data and collections/biobanks that maintain material samples used (or potentially used) for omic analyses. Initial partners might include:
 - **Global Genome Biodiversity Network (GGBN)** - the Global Genome Biodiversity Network is an international network of institutions that share an interest in long-term preservation of genomic samples representing the diversity of non-human life on Earth.
 - **Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF)** - an international network and research infrastructure funded by the world's governments and aimed at providing anyone, anywhere, open access to data about all types of life on Earth.
 - **IOC/UNESCO Ocean Biodiversity Information System (OBIS)** - a global open-access data and information clearing-house on marine biodiversity for science, conservation and sustainable development.

¹While not engaged as a partner, the foundational capacities of the **International Nucleotide Sequence Database Collaboration (INSDC)** - a long-standing initiative that operates between DDBJ, EMBL-EBI and NCBI, trusted long-term repositories for sequence data - will be used as a sustained archive for all sequence data, as standard in the field.

3. Standards and Best-Practice Organizations - organizations developing (meta)data policies, standards, and best-practice protocols related to the omic observing value chain. Initial partners and collaborators might include:

- **Genomic Standards Consortium (GSC)** - an open-membership working body formed in September 2005 to enable genomic data integration, discovery and comparison through international community-driven standards. The GSC board includes institutional connections to INSDC.
- **Biodiversity Information Standards (TDWG)** - develops, ratifies and promotes standards and guidelines for the recording and exchange of data about organisms; acts as a forum for discussing all aspects of biodiversity information management through meetings, online discussions, and publications.
- **IOC/UNESCO Ocean Best Practices System (OBPS)** - a global, sustained system comprising technological solutions and community approaches to enhance management of methods as well as support the development of ocean best practices. Omic BON will broker its multi-ecosystem methods (including terrestrial, atmosphere, etc) to thematically focused systems such as the OBPS, while reducing members' archiving burdens.

4. Global Earth and Ocean observing programmes - in addition to other BONs in GEO (e.g. MBON), initial partners might include:

- **Global Ocean Observing System (GOOS)** - an IOC-UNESCO coordinated programme, with regional alliances which bridges innovation, science, and operational networks. Its Biology and Ecosystems (BioEco) Panel is developing and implementing [Essential Ocean Variables](#) (EOVs), which can all benefit from omic augmentation. Discussions are already underway to this effect, through GLOMICON-linked initiatives. The potential to align the GOOS EOVs to the GEO BON EBVs with respect to omics-enabled biodiversity observation is of high strategic value.
- **UN Decade of Ocean Science for Sustainable Development (UN Ocean Decade)** - Multiple programme proposals under evaluation feature multi-omic/biomolecular observing components, some with existing links to Omic BON. Should these be successful, we will actively engage them to build collaborations.

Members

Other programs, projects, and initiatives are invited to join Omic BON as **Members** with input to governance through a "General Assembly". Examples of potential Members to be invited include, but are not limited to:

- Partnership for Observation of the Global Ocean ([POGO](#))
- International Long-Term Ecological Research ([ILTER](#))
- World Association of Marine Stations ([WAMS](#)) - IOC/UNESCO network of regional and national networks of marine laboratories
- International Barcode of Life ([IBOL](#))
- Autonomous Reef Monitoring Structures ([ARMS](#)) Global ARMS Program (Smithsonian)
- Ocean Sampling Day ([OSD](#))
- Internet of Samples ([iSamples](#))
- Pensoft Publishers ([Pensoft](#))

Participants

Individuals can join as **Participants**.

Further, in its initial months of operation, Omic BON will convene a task team to develop a diversity, inclusivity, and equity strategy to ensure that the interests and operational realities in the BON's scope are well represented.

Statement about data policies or how the data will be made open access

Good data and information stewardship is essential for inclusive science. Many of our key partners focus on data management and best practice development and have built and expanded the foundation for good data management in our community. We will be building on this, addressing the need for data management from the very start by having a dedicated group within Omic BON to provide guidance on data and information practices, and to address upcoming challenges in data management.

Omics data encapsulates genomics, transcriptomics, proteomics, and metabolomics data. To ensure that these data can be integrated, understood, and reused, such data need to be complemented by metadata records and provenance data.

FAIR and open data management

For each data type, we will be supporting the adherence to the [FAIR](#) (Findable - Accessible - Interoperable - Reusable) data principles.

To share FAIR and open data, partners will be asked to make their data available in the appropriate open, trusted, and long-term repositories using standard formats. Initial recommendations include:

Genomics and transcriptomics (nucleotide sequence) data

- [INSDC](#) resources ([DDBJ](#), [ENA](#), [GenBank](#)), and the recommended file format (FASTQ)

Occurrence data

- [OBIS](#) or [GBIF](#) using file formats and (meta)data standards currently being explored by both TDWG and the GSC

Proteomics data

- [ProteomeXchange](#) databases (e.g., [PRIDE Archive](#), [PeptideAtlas](#)) and the recommended file formats (RAW files for mass spectrometer output, mzTab and mzIdentML for result files along with corresponding peak files, .dat and .msf files for software output)

Metabolomics data

- [MetabolomeXchange](#) databases (e.g., [MetaboLights](#), [NIH workbench](#)) and the recommended file formats (ISA-Tab format)

To further support findability, interoperability, and essentially, reusability, any such records need to be accompanied with metadata records, method descriptions, and (in case of performed in-situ analysis) code and documentation.

Metadata

We will promote agreement on and adherence to relevant metadata standards and will provide guidance on this to support awareness and adoption.

For the omics community relevant metadata standards may be:

- GSC's [MixS checklist](#) (Yilmaz et al., 2011)
 - with a core list, extensions for different omics approaches to describe procedure relevant metadata, and environmental packages to describe sampling site relevant metadata
 - use of ontology terms where possible to support interoperability
- TDWG's [Darwin Core](#) for general biodiversity data (Wieczorek et al., 2012)
- [iSamples](#), [DiSSCo](#), and GGBN for material samples and associated metadata
- Ecological Metadata Language (EML) for dataset descriptions and project metadata, citation and usage license.

To further support the users, we will be working with the relevant standards organisations and communities to work towards interoperability on the standards level.

Acknowledging that there is no one dedicated repository to store the whole of metadata, we request that all metadata records are linked to one another and the core data through permanent identifiers.

Methods

We encourage all participating observatories to publish their SOPs in trusted and open repositories that allow version control and issue persistent identifiers (e.g., citable DOIs) to be added to the metadata records. In its initial phase of operation, methodological recommendations from Omic BON members will be solicited. We will endeavour to integrate compilations of these methods - along with links to the data they generate - into the [BON in a Box](#) framework to enhance portability and integration to systems such as the [Ocean Best Practices System](#) (OBPS) and collections in, e.g., [protocols.io](#).

Further, we will encourage capacity exchange and technology transfer across partners, particularly supporting those in lower-capacity settings. For methods which require resources which are not widely accessible, we will request that members suggest lower-capacity - but maximally compatible - substitutes to promote inclusivity while maintaining observational coherence.

Code

To address the need for *in silico* reproducibility, we will convene task teams to identify community good/best practices for code management and archiving.

Examples of archiving options: Partners will be asked to provide one of the following as part of their metadata records

1. permanent links to Jupyter, R notebook(s) or equivalents
2. permanent links to stable releases of their version-controlled repository

In each of the above cases, guidance and documentation for all the steps taken to perform the in-silico analysis should be included. In case 1., code and documentation are integrated. In case 2., in-line comments may be provided, however, these are not generally sufficient as documentation. In those cases, a step-by-step protocol on how and when to run each script needs to be provided as part of the repository.

Data publications

We will create recommendations and guidelines to enable all participants to use data publications in pursuit of credited and high-quality (meta)data management and publishing. These include increasingly machine-actionable Data Management Plans (Miksa et al., 2019) and Data Papers.

Sensitive data

We will assemble a dedicated task team to explore the handling of sensitive omic data (e.g., occurrence data of endangered and protected species that may be compromised if occurrence data are released).

Ethical data management

To ensure ethical data stewardship, we will additionally put a strong emphasis on the relevant ethical data management guidances. Where appropriate, we strongly encourage all partners to adhere to the:

- [CARE](#) (Collective benefit - Authority to control - Responsibility - Ethics) principles for Indigenous Data Governance
- [First Nations Principles of OCAP](#) (Ownership - Control - Access - Possession)
- [Nagoya Protocol](#) on Access and Benefit sharing by the Convention on Biological Diversity

Where needed, this will be supported through guidance from Omic BON, including recommendation of best practices and tools such as [Biocultural Labels](#) (Anderson & Hudson, 2020).

Statement about which BON partners are already involved in GEO, GEO BON or one of its working groups

“The Genomic Observatories Network is a collaboration between the Group on Earth Observations Biodiversity Observation Network (GEO BON) and the Genomic Standards Consortium (GSC), which held its first coordinated action in the form of Ocean Sampling Day (OSD) on 21 June 2014 and repeated it on the same day in 2015 (Kopf et al., 2015). The effort was joined by a number of GOs Network (marine) sites with the purpose of coordinated, standardised collection and sequencing of seawater throughout the world’s oceans.” (Bruford et al., 2017)

As mentioned above, Omic BON complements other BONs and anticipates active collaboration where appropriate. For example, some of our founding members are coordinating with MBON on closely related, coordinated proposals to the Intergovernmental Oceanographic Commission (IOC) and UNESCO.

Statement about which biodiversity variables are being observed by the Omic BON or its anticipated members.

As they target the very code of life, omic technologies can provide insight into all the EBV classes at some level. However, the initial foci are likely to be:

- **Genetic composition**
 - This EBV may be directly empowered by the (meta)genomic capacities which Omic BON will rally and align. With its partners focusing on data management and best practice development, Omic BON will support this EBV by suggesting harmonised approaches to assess the co-ancestry, allelic diversity, population genetic differentiation, and breed and variety diversity sub-variables can be pursued as omic technologies and methods evolve.
- **Community composition**
 - Amplicon sequencing and the extraction of phylogenetic markers from (meta)genomic/(meta)transcriptomic data sets is widely used to assess **taxonomic/phylogenetic diversity** in both macro- and microscale ecosystems. As more reference databases emerge, the resolution and coverage of omic diversity assessment are set to increase. Omic technologies can also provide indirect insight into an assemblages potential **trait diversity** and **interaction diversity**, especially when the traits and/or interactions in question are not directly observable. This can be an asset when assessing the potential plasticity of ecosystems and their communities.
- **Species populations**
 - The same omic technologies relevant for community composition EBVs can be applied to the assessment of **species distribution** and - with calibration - estimates of **species abundances**. This is especially valuable where direct observations are not tractable but where calibrated eDNA and/or microbiome-based omics surveys are deployable. Functional and phylogenetic markers of species or phylotypes (where species concepts are not applicable) can fill gaps in distribution models, and provide some (qualified) bearing on abundances. Omic BON will be able to provide assessment on how to ingest and qualify such estimates in the work and operational contexts of other BONs.
- **Species traits**
 - Assessing the genomic potential, the transcription (and thus expression) of, and proteomic presence of biological components of cells can provide insight into the **physiology** and **morphology** sub-variables where other observations are missing, especially for microbial life.
 - **Phenology** is also approachable through omic observations, and can deepen or complement other observations when omics targets residual DNA signatures left behind by, e.g., migratory species that were not directly observed.

In addition to the main focal points above, Omic BON activities can also contribute to deepening GEO BON's ecosystem-level EBVs. Particularly, through genome- and metagenome-scale approaches (as well as their transcriptomic counterparts), omic

technologies offer insight into the functional potential of ecological assemblages. Through pooling genomic, transcriptomic, proteomic (or their meta-omic counterparts), and metabolomic data across organisms in an ecosystem, high-resolution insight can be obtained to complement other measures of **ecosystem functioning and structure**. In an ecosystem where direct observation of indicator species is difficult or prohibitive, (meta)genomic markers can also be used to determine boundaries and ecotone signatures to augment measures of **ecosystem distribution and extent**.

In pursuing Omic BON's mission, we will seek to coordinate with other BONs (e.g., MBON, see Figure 3) to ensure coherent application of multi-omic approaches, which have high sensitivity to change and are largely ecosystem agnostic. This is particularly valuable as deploying such approaches are falling in line with the EBV requirement of being technically feasible, economically viable, and sustainable in time. Additionally, such coordination is becoming increasingly urgent as other EV development communities targeting life (e.g., the GOOS Biology and Ecosystem EOVs) are turning to multi-omic techniques.

Figure 3. Illustration of the thematic overlap of Essential Variable (EV) initiatives. All sectors where biological EVs are involved are readily linkable to the operations and activities of Omic BON.

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